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A Case Study on A 76-Year-Old Housewife, Diagnosed with Schizophrenia

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Abstract

Schizophrenia is a severe mental illness marked by several strange behaviors, including hearing voices (hallucinations), distorted or false perceptions, and unconventional ideas. Many people do not know much about this disorder or think they do, but their views are incorrect. People imagine some ridiculous behavior of a person with Schizophrenia and typical misconceptions about this type of disorder, bringing up pictures of a person with untidy looks, messy hair, and ripped clothes. In this matter, the researcher aimed to understand Schizophrenia better, recognize the signs and symptoms, and find and access the care and support they need. This study utilizes an interview with the second eldest daughter of the 76-year-old housewife, who was suspected of having symptoms of Schizophrenia in 1993, but it was only confirmed in 2013. The researcher gathered the necessary information, including the cause of the disorder, signs and symptoms, treatment strategies, and scientific breakthroughs. Findings revealed that one of the interactions of the 76-year-old housewife was between genes and personal, familial, social, educational, occupational, and other vital areas of life are usually accompanied by severe suffering and impairment (e.g., the death of the husband and what she sees around may be the reason to remember him) cause the disorder. There is no known treatment for Schizophrenia, but different methods and techniques can assist the individual in living freely. These numerous ways and strategies have prescribed a combination of drugs, therapy, and rehabilitation. However, in the case of this 76-year-old housewife, she has been prescribed only an antipsychotic medication (Clozapine). Moreover, if the 76-year-old had been treated early and had enough money for treatment strategy and a stable support system, it might not have led to such severe mental illness. Thus, to avoid such a large gap in the treatment of mental illness, there must be a health action plan outlining the procedures necessary to offer appropriate assistance to those suffering from mental illnesses such as Schizophrenia. One significant proposal of the action plan is to move services from facilities to the community so that more individuals can access quality, affordable mental health treatment.

Keywords: *schizophrenia, behaviors, hallucinations*

Introduction

Schizophrenia is a severe mental illness marked by many strange behaviors, including hearing voices (hallucinations), distorted or false perceptions, and unconventional ideas. Unfortunately, they cannot tell the difference between genuine and imagined experiences. Others think that the individual is lost in their world since these unique encounters appear genuine to them (Svoboda, 2021). Because of the symptoms of Schizophrenia, a person with the disorder is prone to interpret reality in an atypical way to others. They may believe that people are attempting to control or hurt them, and they may feel forced to act in ways that look odd to others, such as closing all doors and windows to protect the family from the neighbors' attempts to murder or damage them. Furthermore, Schizophrenia patients are unaware of the changes in their behavior. They may refuse to acknowledge behaving differently (D'Arrigo, 2020). This is because the distinctions between exterior and internal reality are distorted for them, and they cannot distinguish between the two. Because of their lack of understanding, they retreat from family and friends and refuse medical assistance.

According to World Health Organization (2022), Schizophrenia affects approximately 24 million people or 1 in 300 people (0.32%) worldwide. This rate is 1 in 222 people (0.45%) among adults (2). It is not as widespread as many other mental illnesses. Onset occurs most frequently in late adolescence and the twenties, and men and women are equally affected by Schizophrenia (Mueser & McGurk, 2004). Psychosocial conditions may also play a role in the occurrence and progression of schizophrenia. Some factors are believed to put a person at a greater risk of developing Schizophrenia, such as genetic factors, a chemical imbalance in the brain, personal, familial, social, educational, occupational, and other vital areas of life are usually accompanied by severe suffering and impairment, and problems during pregnancy (White Swan Foundation, 2015).

On the daily basis, we have a typical misconception about this type of disorder, and we bring up pictures of a person with an untidy look, messy hair, and ripped clothes. Also, an individual unable to manage his or her behaviors and whose conduct is erratic and aggressive; someone who communicates with UFOs or behaves possessed. People with Schizophrenia have been portrayed in movies as quirky geniuses or insane and violent people who need to be locked up in a mental institute for the rest of their lives. However, this is not the real case and clinical diagnosis of a person with symptoms of Schizophrenia. Thus, this study aims to understand Schizophrenia better and recognize its signs and symptoms. Many people do not know much about this disorder or think they do, but their ideas are not right. Through this research, we can help people find and access the care and support they need.

Etiology of the Disorder

A 76-year-old housewife was suspected of having symptoms of Schizophrenia in 1993, but it was only confirmed in 2013. She is a

modest woman who rarely leaves the house because she grows vegetables while caring for her eight children. On the other hand, her husband was a farmer driver who delivered vegetables and rice grains to various parts of Bohol to support the family. According to her second eldest daughter, the couple's life was very peaceful because they did not fight and were tender to each other. Although she has eight children, it has never been a burden to her because her children were trained to help with household chores, the older siblings can be left to look after the younger siblings, and they also know how to plant. All in all, their family can be described as a beautiful and peaceful family. However, all the good events in their lives were changed on August 15, 1992, where the day of the husband's accident due to a concussion while on his way home from a town fiesta. That is where the 76-year-old housewife's unusual behavior began.

Clinical Symptoms

A person with schizophrenia is unlikely to behave strangely all of the time. The symptoms might arrive and subside at random, and the degree of the strange experience varies (Healthline, 2017). This condition has marked symptoms that can evolve and even improve over time.

The 76-year-old housewife first observed unusual behavior a month after her husband's death was being in a stupor in absence, lacking interest in eating, having difficulty sleeping, and having a world of her own. In the following months and years, they could somehow talk to their mother usually, but they saw and knew that there was a massive difference in the way she behaved compared to normal human behavior. Until many years have passed, her behavior has become severe and can be said to be unusual or abnormal.

According to her second eldest daughter, they now clearly observed that their mother avoided spending time with them, and she preferred being alone, speaking in a flat, monotonous tone to them. Second, they were also alarmed because her mother saw or heard something that did not exist and reached the point that her mother experienced tasting, touching, or smelling something that was not there. Third, her mother also becomes paranoid when her siblings have wounds on their heads, maybe because she is afraid that what happened to her husband will also happen to her children. Moreover, lastly, she has trouble paying attention to what other people are saying and may forget even to do simple routine tasks.

Impact of the Disorder

The family has changed a lot, especially in their lives. The husband's death in an accident can still be mourned, but the gradual despair of the 76-year-old housewife seems to be a cumbersome burden on the abandoned eight children. When it comes to the disorder's impact, none of the diagnosed people can identify its impact, but the left-behind children would be burdened with its effect. The burden is considered in terms of objective effects, such as illness severity or financial output, and subjective effects; such as the emotional impact of the illness on a family member.

Over the years, all the mother's responsibilities have automatically passed to the children, and they can no longer approach their mother and cannot feel the care and love from a mother. No one could guide them in growing up and support them throughout their life journey. They were also financially struggling because there was no one to fund them, only the second eldest daughter's small salary from a small private school to sustain their lives then. Their lives have become problematic, especially when they see their mother in such a situation, and no matter what they do, they cannot do anything because they do not have money.

Treatment Strategies

Medical experts have not been able to pinpoint the specific causes of schizophrenia, according to the White Swan Foundation (2015). As a result, no one test can be used to diagnose schizophrenia. While there is no known cure for schizophrenia, there are somehow numerous therapies that can help the person live independently (Healthline, 2017).

In the referral of the 76-year-old housewife to the hospital, the psychiatrist first established a diagnosis following a comprehensive clinical examination because of the variety of symptoms that had been observed in the patient. Second, the psychiatrist understands the alterations in the behavior and bodily functioning as part of the assessment (sleeplessness, lack of interest in eating or socializing). Third, the family was asked for information on the patient's behavioral abnormalities. Upon gathering questions from the family, it was found that they have a relative who also has a mental illness on the side of the 76-year-old housewife, and this is her first-degree cousin. Thus, one of the psychiatrist's diagnoses was the interaction between genes and personal, familial, social, educational, and occupational. Other vital areas of life are usually accompanied by severe suffering and impairment (e.g., the death of the husband and what she sees around may be the reason to remember him) cause the disorder.

According to what has been mentioned above, there is no known treatment for schizophrenia, but different methods and techniques can assist the individual in living freely. These numerous ways and strategies have prescribed a combination of drugs, therapy, and rehabilitation. However, in the case of this 76-year-old housewife, she has been prescribed only an antipsychotic drug.

Below is the breakdown of her medication from 2013 until now

<i>Year</i>	<i>Medicine</i>	<i>Milligram (Mg)</i>	<i>Dosage</i>
2013-Present	Clozapine Syclop	25 Mg	Maintenance Evening (After Meal At Exactly 8 Pm)

She always took the above medications until now, and thankfully, her children have no difficulty getting to drink this tablet to their mother. Unfortunately, in April 2018, she was rushed to the hospital because blood came from her mouth when she coughed. Another test was performed, and it was found that her blood pressure was very high. According to Mayo Clinic (2021), a person with mental illness has a surge of hormones in a stressful situation. These hormones temporarily increase blood pressure by causing the heart to beat faster and blood vessels to narrow. Moreover, upon reviewing the side effects of the prescribed medicine for schizophrenia (Clozapine), it was discovered that the common side effect of antipsychotic drugs for second-generation antipsychotics is hypertension (Murray & Picchioni, 2007). Therefore, the doctor decided to prescribe additional medication for her high blood pressure (Hypertension) with the psychiatrist's permission.

Below is the breakdown of her additional medication currently.

<i>Year</i>	<i>Medicine</i>	<i>Milligram (Mg)</i>	<i>Dosage</i>
2013-Present	Clozapine SYCLOP	25 mg	Maintenance Evening (After Meal At Exactly 8 Pm)
2018-Present	Amlodipine LOBIDES	10 mg	Maintenance Evening (After Meal At Exactly 8 Pm)

Results and Discussion

Before this study began, this disorder was never familiar to ordinary people (including the researcher) because the only thing people know when talking about mental illnesses is depression and anxiety. Though schools, governments, and NGOs hold symposiums and seminars, much of the focus goes again to depression and anxiety, as these two are the most prevalent mental health disorders. However, schizophrenia is not given as much attention.

Many misconceptions have been arising about schizophrenia because many people still do not see a person with schizophrenia in how they behave and act. Thus, people imagine some ridiculous behavior of a person with schizophrenia. Moreover, it is inconceivable that many did bear this kind of disorder and never acknowledged its suffering due to a lack of understanding and lack of assistance from the government. The affected family members also do not know how to manage (in all aspects) this kind of disorder, especially for the unfortunate family, because, again, no one supports this disorder. In fact, WHO (2021) found that none of the objectives for effective mental health leadership and governance, community-based mental health services, mental health promotion and prevention, or information system enhancement were close to being met. Because of that, mental hospitals are ineffective at delivering the treatment that individuals with mental health issues require and violate the fundamental human rights of persons with schizophrenia. The vast majority of people with schizophrenia worldwide are not receiving mental health care. Schizophrenia affects almost half (50%) of all persons in psychiatric facilities. Only 31.3 percent of those who have psychosis receive specialized mental health treatment. Most mental health service resources are inefficiently spent on care within mental institutions (WHO, 2022). Consequently, this prompted the researcher to appreciate the information obtained in the interview of the 76-year-old housewife's daughter. It also changed the researcher's perspective to appreciate and pay attention to schizophrenia and further do research even more.

Conclusions

The journey of the children, especially the 76-year-old housewife, has not been easy as they have not been able to treat their mother quickly due to lack of money. If their mother had been treated early and had enough money for treatment strategy and a stable support system, it might not have led to such severe mental illness, and they may have been able to feel their mother's affection.

On the brighter side, the medication treatment of the 76-year-old housewife has been progressively successful from 2013 until now. Over time, her children can see that her speech is progressing, she interacts more with others, and the general symptoms of anxiety, delusion, guilt, tension, and poor attention or judgment have now disappeared. Another reason acknowledged as positive progress is the constant communication and visits with her eight children and grandchildren. They see that the 76-year-old housewife has changed and is happy when the children all go home. The children have never made their mother feel that she is a burden and has a disorder. Instead, they always hug and kiss her to express that they love their mother very much.

People have gone through so much in their struggle with mental health, and it is sad because only a small percentage of attention is devoted to mental health. If only this were addressed and provided with adequate financial and additional support from the law, it would not lead to a large gap in the treatment of mental illness, just like what the 76-year-old housewife experienced on the journey of her schizophrenia. There must be a health action plan outlining the procedures necessary to offer appropriate assistance to those suffering from mental illnesses such as schizophrenia. One significant proposal of the action plan is to move services from facilities to the community so that more individuals have access to quality, affordable mental health treatment.

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